

TEACHER OCCUPATIONAL BURNOUT AND WORK TASK MOTIVATION

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Abstract: This study is aimed to find out the relationship between teacher occupational burnout and work task motivation. This study utilized the non-experimental quantitative research design using descriptive technique involving teachers in Davao Occidental Division, Philippines. The study was conducted on the second semester of School Year 2025-2026. Research instruments on teacher occupational burnout and work task motivation were used as source of data. Using mean and pearson-r as statistical tools to treat the data, the study showed the following results: The study found to exhibit a high level of teacher occupational burnout. This means that the provisions relating to teacher occupational burnout is oftentimes observed. The study revealed a high level of work task motivation. This indicates that the provisions relating to work task motivation are embodied in the item is oftentimes observed. The results of the study also confirm that there is a significant relationship between teacher occupational burnout and work task motivation. This implies that the higher the teacher occupational burnout, the lower is the teacher occupational burnout. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between teacher occupational burnout and work task motivation was rejected.

Keywords: teacher occupational burnout, work task motivation, school administration and supervision, quantitative research.

I. INTRODUCTION

Work task motivation refers to the level of energy, effort, and enthusiasm an teacher brings to completing tasks at work. For teachers, work task motivation plays a vital role in their daily professional lives, influencing their commitment to teaching, student engagement, and the overall success of the school. Motivated teachers are more likely to innovate, engage with students meaningfully, and contribute positively to the school culture. However, various problems can hinder teachers' motivation to perform their tasks effectively, ultimately affecting their well-being and the quality of education provided to students. Understanding these motivational challenges is crucial for addressing underlying issues and improving teacher performance and satisfaction (Criado-Del Rey, Portela-Pino, Domínguez-Alonso & Pino-Juste, 2024).

There is a low level of work motivation among teachers in the United States mainly due to students behavior. In classrooms, students are unmotivated and lack respect for the teacher, which becomes difficult to foster a productive learning environment. Teachers feel that their efforts are not yielding positive results, leading to a decrease in their motivation to continue putting in the necessary effort (Twardawski & Hilbig, 2022).

In Lebanon, the issue on work task motivation among teachers have reached a high point due to some students who lack engagement which influenced teachers' work task motivation. When students are disengaged or exhibit disruptive behavior, teachers often experience frustration and a sense of ineffectiveness, which can directly impact their motivation (Rouadi, Anouti & Mchiek, 2020).

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In the Philippines, another major issue affecting work task motivation is the increasing workload and administrative burden placed on teachers which has affected around 75% of teachers. In addition to their teaching responsibilities, many educators are tasked with handling administrative duties, participating in meetings, preparing reports, and engaging in extracurricular activities. This heavy workload can lead to physical and emotional exhaustion, reducing teachers' energy levels and diminishing their motivation to perform core teaching tasks. As the demands of teaching expand, teachers may struggle to balance their professional responsibilities with their personal well-being, which can lower their job satisfaction and motivation to engage meaningfully with their students (Magalong & Torreon, 2021).

In the local setting, work task motivation is critical for ensuring that teachers remain engaged, effective, and satisfied in their roles. However, various factors such as lack of recognition, overwhelming workloads, limited professional development, lack of autonomy, and student behavior can undermine teachers' motivation and well-being. By understanding these challenges and addressing the root causes, educational institutions can help foster an environment where teachers are motivated to perform at their best, ultimately benefiting both the teachers themselves and the students they serve.

This study seeks to underscore the relationship between teacher occupational burnout and work task motivation to ascertain the relationship between the two variables. Today, the researcher has rarely come across with a study on the study regarding these two variables. It is in this context that the researcher prompted to conduct this study and to address geographical gap.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE**Statement of the Problem**

This study is aimed to find out the relationship between teacher occupational burnout and work task motivation. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following objectives:

1. What is the level of teacher occupational burnout in terms of:
 - 1.1 Exhaustion;
 - 1.2 Mental Distance;
 - 1.3 Cognitive Impairment, and
 - 1.4 Emotional Impairment?
2. What is the level of work task motivation in terms of:
 - 2.1 Class Preparation;
 - 2.2 Teaching;
 - 2.3 Evaluation of Students;
 - 2.4 Administrative Tasks, and
 - 2.5 Complementary Tasks?
3. Is there a significant relationship between teacher occupational burnout and work task motivation?

Hypothesis

Ho1. There is no significant relationship between teacher occupational burnout and work task motivation.

III. METHODOLOGY**Research Design**

This study employed non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing correlational technique. Non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing a correlational technique is a type of research approach used to examine the relationship between two or more variables without manipulating them. It falls under quantitative research because it involves collecting and analyzing numerical data. The term non-experimental indicates that the researcher does not control or manipulate any variables, unlike in experimental research, where treatments or interventions are applied.

Non-experimental correlational research is a research design used to determine whether and to what degree a relationship exists between two or more quantifiable variables, without establishing cause and effect in which in this study, it will look into the relationship between teacher occupational burnout and work task motivation.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tools were used in the analysis of data.

Mean. This will be used to determine the level of teacher occupational burnout and work task motivation.

Pearson r. This will be used to determine the significance of the relationship between teacher occupational burnout and work task motivation.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Teacher Occupational Burnout

Shown in Table 1 is the level of teacher occupational burnout with an overall mean of 4.09 with a descriptive equivalent of high indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes observed. The overall mean was the result obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which was appended in this study.

Among the enumerated indicators, exhaustion, has the highest mean rating with a mean score of 4.21 or very high, cognitive impairment, 4.08 or high, emotional impairment, 4.08 or high, and mental distance, 4.05 or high. The result of the study corresponds with the statement of Nwoko, Emeto, Malau-Aduli & Malau-Aduli (2023) who declared that teacher occupational burnout is a psychological, emotional, and physical condition resulting from prolonged exposure to chronic stress and excessive demands in the teaching profession. It is characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment. Burnout often arises when teachers face high workloads, inadequate resources, lack of support, unclear expectations, or persistent challenges in managing student behavior and administrative tasks. Over time, burnout can negatively impact teachers’ health, job satisfaction, professional commitment, and ultimately, student learning outcomes.

Table 1. Teacher Occupational Burnout

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Levels
Exhaustion	4.21	Very High
Mental Distance	4.05	High
Cognitive Impairment	4.08	High
Emotional Impairment	4.08	High
Overall	4.10	High

The result of the study is consistent with the statement of Alsalhe, Chalghaf, Guelmami, Azaiez & Bragazzi (2021) who noted that the consequences of teacher burnout extend beyond individual well-being. Emotionally exhausted teachers may exhibit decreased motivation, lower instructional quality, and reduced engagement with students. Burnout can also affect classroom climate, leading to diminished student-teacher relationships and decreased student engagement. Chronic occupational stress may increase absenteeism, teacher turnover, and a negative school culture, which undermines overall organizational effectiveness.

The result of the study supports the statement of Mijakoski, D., Cheptea, Marca, Shoman, Caglayan, Bugge & Canu (2022) who expressed that addressing teacher occupational burnout requires a combination of individual and organizational strategies. Teachers can benefit from stress management techniques, self-care practices, time management, and professional development that builds coping skills and resilience. Schools and districts can support teachers by providing manageable workloads, clear expectations, administrative support, mentorship programs, and fostering a positive, collaborative school climate. By mitigating the causes of burnout and promoting professional well-being, schools can sustain teacher effectiveness and enhance student achievement.

Level of Work Task Motivation

Shown in Table 2 is the level of work task motivation with an overall mean of 4.12 with a descriptive equivalent of very high indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes observed. The overall mean was the result obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which was appended in this study.

Among the enumerated indicators, teaching has the highest mean rating with a mean score of 4.14 or high, evaluation of students, 4.14 or high, class preparation, 4.13, complementary tasks, 4.10 or high, and administrative tasks, 4.0 or high.

The result of the study reflects the statement of Erarslan & Asmah (2022) who noted that Teacher work task motivation is essential because it directly influences instructional quality, classroom effectiveness, and student achievement. Motivated teachers invest time and energy in lesson planning, instructional innovation, and meaningful student engagement. They are more likely to demonstrate persistence, creativity, and enthusiasm in their work, which positively affects students' academic performance and motivation to learn. When teachers are highly motivated, they go beyond basic job requirements and actively contribute to school improvement efforts.

The result of the study confirms the statement of Dias, Ratumanan, Souisa & Batlolona (2021) who declared that work task motivation also plays a crucial role in teacher well-being and professional sustainability. Teachers who feel internally driven and supported are less likely to experience burnout, disengagement, or job dissatisfaction. In schools, when teachers are given meaningful input in decision-making, opportunities to develop their skills. The result of the study is in line with the statement of Mishra & Sharma (2023) who expressed that teacher work task motivation contributes to a positive school climate and organizational effectiveness. Motivated teachers collaborate more effectively, participate in professional development, and model enthusiasm and commitment for students. Their positive energy strengthens team dynamics and fosters a culture of excellence.

Table II. Work Task Motivation

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Levels
Class Preparation	4.13	High
Teaching	4.14	High
Evaluation of Students	4.14	High
Administrative Tasks	4.09	High
Complementary Tasks	4.10	High
Overall	4.12	High

Significance on the Relationship between Teacher Occupational Burnout and Work Task Motivation

Illustrated in Table 3 were the results of the test of relationship between variables involved in the study. The overall correlation had a computed value of 0.836 with a probability value of $p < 0.01$ which is significant at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between teacher occupational burnout and work task motivation is rejected.

The result of the study is consistent with the statement of Moulton, Fuzi, Yussoff, Shazali, Mahmud & Rahmat (2022) who commented that The relationship between teacher occupational burnout and work task motivation is significant and inversely related: as burnout increases, work task motivation tends to decrease. Burnout, characterized by exhaustion, mental distance, cognitive impairment, and emotional impairment, drains the psychological and emotional energy teachers need to perform their duties effectively. When teachers experience chronic stress and fatigue, their enthusiasm, persistence, and commitment to tasks such as lesson preparation, teaching, assessment, and administrative work are diminished.

Table III. Significance on the Relationship between Teacher Occupational Burnout and Work Task Motivation

Pair	Variables	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Decision on Ho
IV and DV	Teacher Occupational Burnout and Workplace Professional Practice of Teacher	0.836	0.000	Reject

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The result of the study supports the statement of Hyseni Duraku, Jahiu & Geci (2025) who pointed out that exhaustion reduces the physical and mental energy required to sustain high levels of effort, while mental distance weakens teachers' emotional connection to their work and students. Cognitive impairment affects focus, planning, and decision-making, making even routine tasks feel overwhelming. Emotional impairment reduces empathy and patience, which are critical for effective teaching and student evaluation. Burnout undermines these psychological needs, thereby weakening intrinsic motivation and reducing overall task engagement.

The result of the study is in agreement with the statement of Tan & Kim (2024) who indicated that high work task motivation can serve as a protective factor against burnout. Teachers who find meaning in their work, feel competent in their roles, and experience supportive relationships are more resilient to stress. Positive school leadership, manageable workloads, recognition, and professional growth opportunities can strengthen motivation and reduce burnout risks. Ultimately, the relationship between teacher occupational burnout and work task motivation highlights the importance of fostering supportive school environments that sustain teacher well-being, engagement, and professional effectiveness.

V. CONCLUSION

Based from the findings of the study, conclusions are drawn in this section. The study found to exhibit a high level of teacher occupational burnout. This means that the provisions relating to teacher occupational burnout is oftentimes observed.

The study revealed a high level of work task motivation. This indicates that the provisions relating to work task motivation are embodied in the item is oftentimes observed.

The results of the study also confirm that there is a significant relationship between teacher occupational burnout and work task motivation. This implies that the higher the teacher occupational burnout, the lower is the teacher occupational burnout. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between teacher occupational burnout and work task motivation was rejected.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of this study revealed that there is a high level of teacher occupational burnout. The researcher recommends that teachers may break complex tasks into smaller, manageable steps to reduce cognitive overload; use structured planning tools to organize priorities and avoid multitasking overload; schedule short mental breaks between classes to reset focus; identify repetitive tasks that can be streamlined using templates or digital tools; collaborate with colleagues to share lesson plans and teaching resources; focus energy on high-impact activities that directly influence student learning; establish clear boundaries between work and personal time (e.g., limit after-hours emails or grading); engage in restorative activities such as exercise, hobbies, or spending time with family; incorporate short physical stretches or movement breaks during the day; stay hydrated and maintain balanced nutrition; prepare materials the day before to reduce morning stress, and reconnect with personal purpose and long-term teaching goals.

Principals may review teacher workload to ensure it is balanced and realistic; provide adequate planning periods within the school day; minimize unnecessary meetings and administrative paperwork; respect teachers' personal time by limiting after-hours communication; promote wellness initiatives such as mental health workshops or stress-management training; provide administrative support staff to reduce non-instructional burdens; recognize teacher efforts and achievements regularly; encourage open communication about stress and workload concerns, and build a supportive, team-oriented environment where teachers feel valued and understood.

The study revealed a high level of work task motivation. The researcher recommends that teachers may start recording and transmitting absences by setting a daily routine (e.g., first 5 minutes of class) for accurate attendance recording, communicate promptly with parents/guardians regarding patterns of absenteeism; maintain organized, confidential, and up-to-date documentation using standardized formats, and monitor patterns in behavior to support early intervention strategies.

The principals may provide clear guidelines and standardized templates for attendance and disciplinary documentation; set clear agendas and objectives before meetings; keep meetings time-bound and focused; promote meaningful participation of teachers during meeting; reduce administrative burden by evaluating whether certain tasks can be delegated to support staff.

The results of the study also confirm that there is a significant relationship between teacher occupational burnout and work task motivation. The researcher recommends that they may strengthen personal energy management; enhance intrinsic motivation by reconnecting with professional purpose and the impact of your teaching on students, and communicate workload concerns to school leadership before stress escalates.

Principals may conduct periodic workload reviews to ensure fairness and balance; minimize unnecessary administrative demands that drain teacher energy; foster a motivating school climate; recognize and celebrate teacher achievements regularly; address burnout proactively; provide professional development on stress management and resilience.

District supervisors may strengthen leadership capacity by providing principals with training on burnout prevention, motivational leadership, and supportive supervision; develop system-level support structures by implementing district-wide wellness programs for educators; review policies that unintentionally increase administrative burden and promote sustainable motivation systems by aligning evaluation systems with professional growth rather than punitive measures.

The researcher also recommends to future researchers to conduct similar study and explore some indicators that are not included in this study in another setting in order to uncover new knowledge relevant to the topics presented in this study.

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